

ADVANCED CHARACTERIZATION OF POLYMERS AND COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING AXIAL-TORSIONAL DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

José Alberto Rodríguez Agudo¹, Matthias Ruf³, Dominik Fauser³, Christopher Giehl¹, Jan Haeberle¹, Jörg Läger¹, Abhishek Shetty², Holger Steeb³, Gunther Arnold¹

¹*Anton Paar Germany GmbH, Ostfildern, Germany;*

²*Anton Paar USA Inc, Ashland, United States*

³*Institute of Applied Mechanics, Chair of Continuum Mechanics, University of Stuttgart, Germany*

Gunther.Arnold@anton-paar.com

AXIAL-TORSIONAL DMA

- Originally, functionality and application scope of DMA and rheometer clearly separated
- Modern high-end rheometers are able to combine a rotational and a linear motor in a single device

Linear Drive

Rotational Drive

- All DMA working modes in one device
- Combine **torsional/extensional measurements** on viscoelastic solids

AXIAL-TORSIONAL DMA

We add one more direction to the characterization of the linear viscoelastic behavior in a single experiment!

- $|G^*|$ and $|E^*|$ obtained on the same specimen in one single measurement and under same conditions

- In accordance to Tschoegl protocol¹

- For isotropic samples → Indirect measurement of the complex Poisson's ratio

$$\nu = -\frac{\varepsilon_{trans}}{\varepsilon_{axial}} \quad \nu^*(\omega, T) = \frac{E^*(\omega, T)}{2 \cdot G^*(\omega, T)} - 1$$

- Measurements on cylindrical specimens (No warping torsion effects^{2,3,4,5})

*1. Tschoegl et al. 2002
*2. Szabó 2013
*3. Dessi et al. 2016
*4. Diani and Gilormini 2017
*5. Dessi et al. 2021

POISSON'S RATIO

EXAMPLE: POLYMETHYL METHACRYLATE

$$\nu^*(\omega, T) = \frac{E^*(\omega, T)}{2 \cdot G^*(\omega, T)} - 1$$

*6. J.R Agudo et al., 2023, *J. Rheol.*

POISSON'S RATIO

COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT POLYMERS

AXIAL-TORSIONAL DMA

ANISOTROPIC MATERIALS

- $|G^*|$ and $|E^*|$ obtained **on the same specimen in one single measurement** and under **same conditions**
- Concept of single Poisson's ratio not valid anymore

For anisotropic samples

Extra information about viscoelastic anisotropy of the sample?

AXIAL-TORSIONAL DMA

POLYPROPYLENE / GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

Blend of isotactic PP and ethylene/1-olefin copolymer rubber

- Polypropylene blend matrix (PP)
- Polypropylene
- 25% glass fiber (PP-GF)
- ◻ Recycled Polypropylene
- △ 25% glass filler (PP-GF-R)

- $\uparrow E^*$ by a factor of 7
- $\uparrow G^*$ by a factor of 2.4
- $\downarrow E^*$ by a factor of 30%
- $\downarrow G^*$ by a factor of 7%

AXIAL-TORSIONAL DMA

POLYPROPYLENE / GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

Blend of isotactic PP and ethylene/1-olefin copolymer rubber

$$\zeta = \tan\delta_G / \tan\delta_E ?$$

AXIAL-TORSIONAL DMA

POLYPROPYLENE / GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

Hypothesis → ζ may behave as a dynamic macroscopic fingerprint unique to each anisotropic structure?

STRUCTURE ANALYSIS

MICRO X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (MXRCT)

Matthias Ruf, Dominik Fauser and Prof.
Steeb: Institute of Applied Mechanics (CE),
University of Stuttgart

1x1x1 mm³ sub-volume

Evaluated fibers ~ 8000

STRUCTURE ANALYSIS

MICRO X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (MXRCT)

Polypropylene and glass fiber reinforced Polypropylene

- Location of fiber regions with the use of a machine learning tool called “Insegt Fibre” - (*7 Emerson et al. 2019)
- Tracking of the fibers by the tool “OpenFiberSeg” - (*8 Sosa-Rey et al. 2022)
 - Fiber length (L_f)
 - Fiber orientation (deviation angle θ and azimuth angle Φ)

Polypropylene 25% glass fiber (PP-GF)

Recycled Polypropylene 25% glass filler

STRUCTURE ANALYSIS

MICRO X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (MXRCT)

Polypropylene and glass fiber reinforced Polypropylene

Polypropylene 25% glass fiber

Recycled Polypropylene 25% glass filler

μ XRCT characterization reveals a statistically significant difference in both the mean fiber length and the mean fiber orientation!

RESULT ANISOTROPIC MATERIAL I

POLYPROPYLENE / GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

PP-GF (25%)

PP-GF (25%) recycled

FURTHER RESULTS

POLYKETONE AND CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYKETONE

FURTHER RESULTS

POLYKETONE AND CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYKETONE

Polyketone

Polyketone (15% CF)

FURTHER RESULTS

POLYKETONE AND CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYKETONE

$\zeta \rightarrow$ **dynamic fingerprint**
unique for each material?

\rightarrow Distinguish anisotropic structures and its dependency on temperature and frequency

- Use of measurements with rotational and axial drive enable determination of $|G^*|$ and $|E^*|$ on the same specimen under the same conditions and in one single experiment
- For homogeneous and isotropic samples → **Complex Poisson's ratio, $|\nu^*|$**
- For anisotropic materials, information of the material in longitudinal and torsional direction can be determined ($E', E'', \tan\delta_E, G', G'', \tan\delta_T$) → $|E^*|/|G^*| = \text{function}(T, f)$
- Results with μ XRCT indicated differences in average fiber size and fiber alignment and hence a different level of anisotropy - as predicted by $\zeta = \tan\delta_G / \tan\delta_E$
- $\zeta = \tan\delta_G / \tan\delta_E$ could be a new dynamic fingerprint unique for each material
 - Distinguish anisotropic structures and its dependency on temperature and frequency → Significant time saving compared to other conventional methods

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

Dr. Gunther Arnold
Product Manager MCR 702e MultiDrive
Rheometry and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

gunther.arnold@anton-paar.com

1. Tschoegl, N.W, Knaus, W.G & Emri, I.(2002) Poisson's ratio in linear viscoelasticity – A critical review. *Mechanics of Time-Dependent Mater*, 6, 3-51.
2. Szabó, I., "Höhere technische Mechanik: nach Vorlesungen," Springer-Verlag (2013).
3. Dessi, C. et al. (2016) Analysis of dynamic mechanical response in torsion. *Journal of Rheology*, 60, 275-287
4. Diani, J., Gilormini, P. (2017). On necessary precautions when measuring solid polymer linear viscoelasticity with dynamic analysis in torsion. *Polymer Testing*, 63, 275-280.
5. Dessi, C., Coppola, S.& Vlassopoulos, D. (2021). Dynamic mechanical analysis with torsional rectangular geometry: A critical assessment of constrained warping models. *Journal of Rheology*, 65, 325-335.
6. Rodriguez Agudo, J.A. et al. (2023). Characterization of the temperature and frequency dependency of the complex Poisson's ratio using a novel combined torsional-axial rheometer. *Journal of Rheology*, 67, 1221-1250.
7. Emerson M et al. (2019). Insegt fibre: A user-friendly software for individual fibre segmentation. *Proceedings of 22nd International Conference on Composite Materials*
8. Sosa-Rey Facundo et al. (2022). Openfiberseg: Open-source segmentation of individual fibers and porosity in tomographic scans of additively manufactured short fiber reinforced composites. *Composites Science and Technology*. 226, 109497